

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Textbook on Linguistics as a space for professional and linguistic self-determination

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Abstract

The article surveys the comparative German and Russian languages typology textbook. The purpose of the research is to provide a reader with the information about the educational process involving the textbook. The emphasis is placed upon the abilities of the textbook to provide students with professional and linguistic self-determination. The feature of the textbook includes two new sections concerning comparative German and Russian languages typology: comparative syntax and comparative lexicology. The theoretical material of the textbook served as a basis for graduate research papers for Bachelor's and Master's Degrees. It is worth mentioning the implementation of a student's professional and linguistic self-determination with the help of the textbook. It implies that the students were able to clarify the important features of similarities and differences of morphological, syntactic and lexicological composition of the compared languages, which were used by the students during their practice at companies, industries and schools.

Keywords: textbook, comparative typology, German and Russian languages.

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Introduction

Bim I.L., as a pioneer in contemporary textbook theory in linguodidactics, noted that a textbook is a «adaptive-adapting» system. It means that, on the one hand, a textbook influences the educational process, and on the other hand, a textbook adapts to the real-life conditions of it (Bim, 1977). Although it referred to the school environment, it seems that, this statement is rather appropriate to describe a textbook on the whole, including high school. The textbooks used in foreign languages faculties must put an emphasis on developing the scope of competence declared at standards and programmes, stay up-to-date to linguistics, introduce to the scientific research methods, and hence, guide the educational process. Besides, the textbook must take into account the personality of a student, and therefore, give them the possibility to “find themselves” in professional linguistics, correlated to the subject. It means that the textbook must be flexible, enabling various classroom organization, providing a student with the opportunity to self-determination and self-fulfillment in the field related to their professional interests.

These are the main points we have taken into consideration while writing the textbook «Comparative typology of German and Russian languages». In this article, we set out the peculiarities of the presentation of the material within the framework of this scientific field in accordance with the characteristics of our textbook (which will enable the reader to get an idea of the organization of the educational process using the textbook), and also emphasize the possibilities of our textbook in the development of professional and linguistic self-determination of students.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the article is to get the reader acquainted with the education process involving the textbook.

The objectives of the study: 1) to give a review on the textbook «Comparative typology of German and Russian languages»; 2) to showcase the opportunities of the textbook for professional and linguistic self-determination of a language college student.

Literature review

A brief linguistic overview in the textbook is presented about studying grammatical categories in comparative study of language and the linguistics of universals based on the numerous works written by FRG linguists devoted to comparison of some particular grammar fields or the grammar system in general.

Partly the textbook may be considered as the legacy of Germanic Studies and Slavic Studies of GDR, and research works on the comparison of German and Slavic languages align with methodological approaches

of East German research projects. It should be mentioned that the research works of Humboldt University of Berlin (Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin), prof. W. Gladrow in particular, a recognized leader in comparative linguistics in Germany (Gladrow 1998, 2001; Gladrow, Heyl, 1996). It must be noted that this research group in collaboration with Russian scientists made a project about contrastive description of German and Russian languages supported by German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft).

Hence, the concept of the textbook is based on the following theory:

- linguistics theories related to functional-semantic and formal-structural peculiarities of language units (Bondarko, 2001; Rakhmankulova, 2005 et al.), the study of language units in comparative aspect (Gladrow, 1998, 2001; Abramov, 2001; Novikova et al., 2018; Shatilova et al., 2020; Biryukova et al., 2020).

- linguodidactics theories, describing the opportunities for professional self-determination of students when studying theoretical and practical foreign language subjects in foreign languages faculties and the role of textbooks in self-determination as a linguistic personality (Bim, 1977; Gal'skova & Gez, 2004; Karaulov, 1989, 2010; Kolesnikov, 2015, 2016).

Methodology

This article represents a scientific description of the characteristics and contents of the new textbook in comparison with the similar already existing ones. The scientific basis underlying the writing of the textbook is generalized. The emphasis is placed on the synthesis of linguistic and linguodidactic theories, which allows to solve two groups of problems simultaneously: mastering linguistic knowledge in the field of comparative typology and the implementation of professional self-determination of the students of foreign languages faculties. A particular attention is paid to the generalization of the empirical experience of using the textbook in the real educational process, the possibilities of organizing independent research students activities on the basis of the textbook are described.

Results

1. Characteristics and content of the textbook «Comparative typology of the German and Russian languages»

The textbook «Comparative typology of German and Russian languages» is aligned with the contents of the Federal State Educational Standard of Higher Education of the New Generation.

According to the curriculum, students during the eighth semester study the comparative typology of the German and Russian languages. And this textbook will complement the existing textbooks, as our textbook contains such material as comparative phraseology, which is covered rather briefly in other textbooks. In addition, the comparative syntax from our textbook is unique. In such a perspective, it is not given in other textbooks on the comparative typology of the German and Russian languages. Students use our textbook with interest for their mini reports during lectures and in their presentations at seminars. These topics include the following:

- Comparative phraseology of the German and Russian languages
- Comparative characteristics of German and Russian word combinations
- Word order in simple sentence in the German and Russian languages
- Peculiarities of word order of compound sentences in the German and Russian languages
- The structure and word order of complex sentence in the German and Russian languages.

The novelty of the textbook implies that it reflected the nature of the contrastive descriptions, which began to focus not on the study of separate language units, but on the comparison of the whole functional-semantic complexes or fields, according to A.V. Bondarko, whose works served as the basis for numerous bilingual contrastive projects. On the material of large groups of closely related and heterogeneous languages, the scientist and his followers carried out a typological description of such categories as voice. It seems important to emphasize the fact that in the textbook the description of syntactic units within the framework of functional grammar in a comparative aspect has found its application and it was possible to consider the functioning of a word combination, a sentence using the example of individual German and Russian texts, taking into account the specifics of their styles (Spitzer, 1928, c.166-222).

The material of the textbook is presented in the terms of Russian traditions, taking into account the trends in the development of Germanic studies and comparative linguistics in recent decades. Topics are included that have not previously been touched upon in educational publications of this type, these include, in particular: the relations of units of different language levels in the study of synonymy, lexical and phraseological systems, categories of types of tense, methods of verb action in the German and Russian languages. This contributes to the expansion of the linguistic scope of competence of students, teaches them a real understanding of the development of the language, the selection and generalization of new linguistic phenomena.

Topics are covered taking into account different linguistic directions. Morphology and syntax are scrutinized from the point of view of functional grammar in a comparative aspect, lexicology – from a traditional point of view in a comparative aspect. At the same time, a definition of concepts is given, approaches are described, and language examples are given.

The textbook covers the basic linguistic disciplines that are studied at the university at the language faculties - theoretical grammar, lexicology. Their consideration in a comparative aspect makes it possible to compare the linguistic facts of a foreign and native language, to study the specifics of languages more deeply. Some topics of theoretical grammar and lexicology are used to review the material covered.

The works of German and Russian writers served as the sources of examples, the materials of German newspapers, as well as the corpus of texts of the Institute of the German Language (Mannheim) and the corpus of texts of the national Russian language.

The textbook emphasizes that the German and Russian languages in the tradition of comparative historical linguistics are marked as related languages: by their origin they belong to the Indo-European (Indo-Germanic) family of languages, however, German is included in the Germanic group (West Germanic subgroup), and Russian is included in the Slavic group (East Slavic subgroup). The closest related languages for the German language are English, Dutch, Frisian, Luxembourgish, Yiddish, Afrikaans, respectively, and for Russian - Ukrainian and Belarusian. Among the many distant related languages are Roman, Celtic, Albanian, Modern Greek and other languages.

For the first time, the textbook analyzes comparative syntax as a promising, developing direction in comparative-historical, typological linguistics, which presents huge opportunities for the study of language units not only within the framework of a sentence and the text, but also for the study of various linguistic levels and their relations in a comparative plan.

In the formal-structural description of syntax in a traditional way, an analysis of the main and secondary members of the sentence is presented. Alongside this, a number of rather controversial issues have emerged related to the typology of the sentence, but have not yet received an unambiguous solution and are scrutinized in the textbook. Besides, semantic, transformational, functional and cognitive models for describing syntax have become widespread and popular, which have not yet been fully developed in the analysis of the languages and do not present the necessary basis for global typological and contrastive descriptions. The same situation is observed in the newest perspectives in the study of syntax – cognitive science, pragmatics and text linguistics.

Comparative study of the vocabulary in the textbook shows the connection between the peculiarity of the language form and the concept when describing the same situation. The comparison of the lexical systems of the two languages raised questions about comparing the functioning of these systems, about the relations between lexical elements and the described reality.

Upon writing this textbook, an emphasis was made towards the refraction of the educational material presented by students in the course of the development of their professional-linguistic self-determination. As A.A. Kolesnikov notes, the universal peculiarity of philological and linguistic education creates the basis for multi-vector professional guidance. It is necessary that the teaching of theoretical and practical disciplines in a foreign language faculty should take into account the variable possibilities of professional self-determination of students (Kolesnikov 2016). According to the famous scientist N.D. Galskova, the result of any language education is a formed linguistic personality, and the result of education in the field of foreign languages is a secondary linguistic personality as an indication of a person's ability to fully participate in intercultural communication (Gal'skova&Gez, 2004). A linguistic personality is a bearer of an autonomous linguistic ability that ensures the production of one's own texts expressing ideals, meaningful values, assumptions necessary to solve a significant task or a problem. The development of a linguistic personality is based on several criteria. The generally acknowledged criterion is the level of language skills, when taken into consideration, makes it possible to build education programs into the system of classes with zero and advanced initial levels in different modes. The second criterion is based on the speaker's attitude to texts and verbal heritage in general.

This model is based on the concept of linguistic personality developed by Yu.N. Karaulov. He defines a linguistic personality as: «a set of abilities and characteristics of a person, determining the creation and perception of speech works, which differ in the degree of structural and linguistic complexity, depth and accuracy of reflection of reality, a certain target orientation» (Karaulov, 1989, p. 3). Yu.N. Karaulov identifies three levels in the structural model of a linguistic personality:

The first level is verbal-semantic, the units of which are separate words as units of the verbally associative network. Students master the structural and system connections of the language under studies in the parameters of the system-forming function of the language, aimed at solving communicative problems.

The second level is linguo-cognitive, the units of which are notions, ideas, concepts that are developed in each linguistic personality into a more or less well-ordered worldview, reflecting the hierarchy of values. Stereotypes at this level correspond to stable standard connections between descriptors, which are expressed in generalized statements, definitions, and catchphrases.

The third level is the motivational level, the units of which are focused on pragmatics and appear, according to Yu.N. Karaulov, in the "communicative-activity needs of the individual" (Karaulov, 2010, p. 57).

Thus, this textbook not only gives an idea of the verbal-semantic and thesaurus content of languages, but also connects the motivational-pragmatic level, which is the research activity of the student himself. And due to it, the student gets the opportunity for self-determination and self-realization in professional linguistic activity, which simultaneously contributes to his establishment as a professional linguist and the development of the structures of a linguistic personality.

2. Practical usage of textbook material in GFL classroom at a university

Let us turn to the practice of using this textbook material by students studying in the field of "Pedagogical Education" (the German language) at the Institute of Foreign Languages of Moscow City Pedagogical University. The textbook aroused undeniable research interest when writing graduate qualification works of students who chose topics related to the study of German and Russian lexical systems in a comparative aspect. One of these topics was the consideration of the lexico-semantic representation of the concepts of "trust," "patience," "fidelity," "love" in the linguodidactic aspect. For example, when considering the concept of "trust," student Y.V. Avdeeva turned to comparative analysis of lexemes capable of displaying the concept of "trust" (representation of the conceptual component of the concept) in German. The textbook helped her decide on a number of German lexemes that could convey understanding of trust. Then, following the algorithm of action set forth in the textbook, which consists of a step-by-step description of the semantics of the lexical units allocated for comparison according to the data of monolingual and etymological dictionaries, followed by comparison in order to identify the linguistic and cultural reasons for their identity, she turned to the data of English dictionaries and was able to successfully compare German and English lexemes. Since the mandatory moment of writing the final qualification work is its practical value, the author used journalistic texts presented in high school textbooks for high school students as additional research material. Having studied German and English textbooks she was able to find out which of the tokens, that she had found, have a stable frequency and which do not. In her work, the student made a linguistic commentary on the etymology of these lexemes and presented it to her own students in a form of a cognitive game called "railway stations". She also described the method of conducting such a game for schoolchildren in detail. Thus, the student discovered her ability to develop productive learning technology (the option of "working at railway stations" /Stationenlernen) as a result of scientific activities based on this textbook.

Another example is the graduate qualification work of A. A. Kulik, who studied the phraseological fund of German and English languages that can display the value component of the concept of "patience". The designated textbook material was able to target the student to create a system for comparing German and English proverbs that evaluate patience in these languages. Since the textbook described in detail the principle of comparing the lexemes of the compared languages based on their etymological, linguistic and cultural characteristics, the student was able to make and compare the classification of the German and English proverbs identified by her. And as in previous cases, the student turned to the analysis of school textbook materials to find opportunities for presenting German aphorisms about patience to her own students whose first foreign language is English. This topic so fascinated the Master's degree student that she continued the work she had started, only this time she decided to focus on the material of lexicographic sources as well as the lexical and semantic representation of the conceptual part of this concept in German and Russian. It is important to mention that the principles of comparison set out in our textbooks were assimilated by her and embodied in her own linguistic research.

L. F. Isayeva devoted her graduate qualification work to the comparative analysis of the conceptual component by means of German and Russian lexemes in the linguodidactic aspect. She used the textbook's methodology for comparing the lexical units of these languages as a basis in her research and was able to identify the common and distinctive features of German and Russian lexemes that reveal the concept of fidelity. Further in her work she analyzes the country-specific texts available in school textbooks of grades 6 and 8 (secondary level) in the German language, which also have other lexemes that reveal the concept of loyalty. The analysis of school textbooks showed the presence of other tokens. The student suggested using a number of methods of teaching this vocabulary in German lessons, linking it with the moral education of children. She continued the work she had begun in the framework of her master's degree, turning to a comparative analysis of the use of these lexemes in German and Russian fiction in the first half of the twentieth century.

M.V. Yagudaeva devoted her graduation qualification work to considering the representation of the value component of the concept of love in German and Russian through proverbs in the linguistic aspect. When writing the work, the student turned to the materials of the proposed textbook on comparative lexicology of German and Russian, having learned the main principles of comparative research of proverbs and sayings. In the practical part of the final qualification work Maria Viktorovna turns to the compilation of the classification of proverbs chosen by her and denoting love, using the approach proposed in the textbook as a basis for compiling such classifications. Then, the student offers her own methodological techniques for comparing Russian proverbs with those love proverbs that can be used in German language lessons as a second foreign language in the 10th grade of a comprehensive school.

The principles of classification of lexical units set forth in the textbook, for example, taking into account blood and non-blood kinship when comparing the vocabulary of the thematic sphere of the family, helped other students in writing their final qualification works. An example is the graduation qualification work of I. S. Vorobyeva, devoted to the study of word-forming computer terms of the German language. The principles of selection and systematization of lexical material helped the student in compiling her own techniques for organizing extracurricular classes on word formation in high school where German is studied as the first foreign language.

It was this approach, presented in the textbook, that provided effective assistance to the student I.R. Akhmeev in analyzing the word-forming models of Anglicisms used in German. The student not only proposed his own classification of word-formation models of Anglicisms, but also, having studied the materials of school textbooks on the German language, compiled a list of Anglicisms used in texts. A significant contribution was made by the method of describing the comparison of the lexical units of the two compared languages to the student's desire to continue developing this same topic during his further studies at the master's school where he compares word-forming models of Anglicisms and finds out the specifics of their adaptation in the German and Russian languages on the material of journalistic texts.

The part of the textbook that highlights the general and distinctive features of the syntax of the German and Russian languages was used by student D.V. Gorbachev when writing his final qualification work on the word order in the German, English and Russian languages. Based on the principles of distinguishing the general and distinctive features of the structure of simple and complex sentences and the word order in them, the student reviewed grammatical material in textbooks (where German is a second foreign language) for Grades 5, 8 and 10, making a number of significant comments and suggestions regarding the explanation of grammatical material based on the native Russian language in grade 5 and the first foreign English language in grades 8 and 10. The student offered his own set of training exercises on the word order in the German language.

Summing up the results of the practical use of the materials of the recommended textbook, it should be noted that it finds its application not only while writing graduate qualification works by students, but also in the classroom by the teachers of the Department of Germanic Studies and Linguodidactics. We will tell you about our experience of using this textbook in the classroom on the history of the German language, both in lectures and in seminars. For example, when studying the historical morphology of the German language, we consider in detail with students the formation and development of the category of number, the case of German nouns. At the beginning of the lecture, the process of formation of the named categories in the Indo-European primordial basis is highlighted. Here students speak about the general and

distinctive characteristics of the manifestation of these categories among German and Russian nouns. They are given the additional time in the form of independent work at home to answer a series of questions based on the recommended textbook.

As the time for studying the history of the German language is limited to a small amount of hours, the lectures reveal the history of the formation and the development of such grammatical categories of German verbs as the category of number, person, tense, voice, mood. Once again, the work begins by relying on data on the Indo-European ancestral basis in the form of independent work at home, based on our textbook. At the beginning of this lecture, we listen to students' speeches about the general and specific features of these categories of German and Russian verbs.

Historical morphology prompted student A.A. Skreblo to begin scientific research of the formation of the future tense in the Germanic languages. The student became interested in comparing Old High German, Old Icelandic and Gothic languages, having clarified the principles of comparing languages, highlighted in our textbook in the section on the comparative morphology of German and Russian languages.

Again, in the form of independent work, students are offered to get acquainted with the comparative characteristics of German and Russian adjectives, pronouns, and numerals with the aid of our textbook. The knowledge gained by students is tested in the form of presentations at seminars. This approach aroused the scientific interest of students, who decided to continue to engage in a comparative study of the history of the formation of a number of categories in the form of scientific works. So, I. S. Kharitonova became interested, having studied in the textbook the principles of comparing the parts of speech of the German and Russian languages, in the formation and development of the mixed declension of adjectives in the German language. The student turned to a comparison of the ancient Germanic languages: German, Icelandic and Gothic. Her scientific articles were highly appreciated by the scientific community, she received a second degree diploma at international scientific competitions twice.

Another example is the scientific interest in the formation and development of the category of the gender of German nouns by E.D. Kucherov, who turned to the comparison of Old High German, Old Icelandic and Gothic languages, applying the basic principles of the language comparison set out in our textbook. His scientific articles also took part in international scientific competitions of student papers, having received diplomas of the first and second degrees.

In the history of the German language course, students are offered educational material on the historical syntax of the German language. Our textbook highlights in a rather detailed way, in a comparative aspect the general and distinctive features of the structure of simple, complex sentences and word combinations of

the German and Russian languages. This material is used in lectures on historical syntax. In the form of independent work at home, students are offered to determine the state of the structure of sentences in the Indo-European primordial basis, paying special attention to the word order in the sentence. The results of their independent work obtained by students can also be presented in the form of mini-lectures at the beginning of the lecture on the historical syntax of the German language.

It was the word order of a complex sentence that interested student N.I. Kulinich, who in her scientific articles highlights the process of forming the word order in the German complex sentence. The results she obtained when comparing Old High German, Old Icelandic and Gothic languages in order to establish the peculiarities of the development of the word order of a complex sentence of Germanic languages were highlighted by her in scientific articles that were presented at international competitions of scientific works twice. The student was awarded second place, she received second degree diplomas.

One of the themes of the course of the history of the German language is historical lexicology. At the beginning of the lecture on this topic, students may be offered to get themselves acquainted with our textbook at home, and more specifically with the section on the comparative lexicology of the German and Russian languages, finding out what can be complemented in the historical phraseology of the German language, in word formation.

This approach to the use of the proposed textbook provides the expansion of the linguistic knowledge of students in subjects related to the comparative typology of the German and Russian languages.

This list of topics will provide a stimulus for the development of the professional skills of the future specialists in intercultural communication. For example, the features of the phraseology of the German and Russian languages can be drilled on translations and in a comparative analysis of original and translated feature films, where proverbs and idioms are often used by the characters. Students - the future teachers - can be offered to look into the school textbooks on the German language and make their own theoretical commentary-rule on the peculiarities of the word order of simple and complex sentences, taking into

Discussions

The proposed possibilities of using this textbook are not limited to the listed parameters of the use of its materials in the course of a number of theoretical disciplines and when writing graduate qualification works of students and undergraduates. We consider it quite probable that there is a different angle of approach to the materials presented in the textbook, which raises a number of interesting discussion questions, which the authors of the textbook regard as a good sign of a creative approach to analyzing the

content of the textbook.

Conclusion

To sum up, the peculiarity of this textbook is determined by the fact that, as mentioned above, it presents two new sections on the comparative typology of the German and Russian languages: comparative syntax and comparative lexicology. It was from the content of these sections that students took the theoretical material they needed to write their final qualification papers at the end of the bachelor's and master's degrees. It should be especially noted the implementation of the student's professional-linguistic self-determination based on the textbook, which is as follows. First, the students were able to find out for themselves important features of the similarities and differences in the morphological, syntactic and lexicological composition of the compared languages, which they used during their practice both at enterprises and firms, and in schools. This is reflected, first of all, for example, in the didactic part of their graduation qualifications, on the one hand, and in the reports on practice. Second, in the course of studying, rethinking and implementing the textbook material, students formed an idea of their abilities and capabilities in research, translation and pedagogical activity - which is an indicator of professional self-determination.

Thus, as experience shows, our textbook can find its application both in the classroom on the comparative typology of the German and Russian languages, the history of the German language, and in the writing of graduate qualification works. In addition, the scientific novelty of the proposed textbook materials expands the linguistic level of students' training, arises their scientific interest.

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